

Blockchain Adoption in Enterprises: Opportunities and Challenges

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Abstract: Blockchain is one of the greatest inventions of the 21st century. Since its inception in 2009 to till date, its applicability has increased manyfold in all business operations. Initially, blockchain technology appeared to be too risky for corporate use since it featured a decentralized, peer-to-peer architecture that allowed anyone to join. That began to alter in 2016 with the development of full enterprise platforms by a rising open-source community, including the Ethereum programmable blockchain and Hyperledger, a framework and set of tools for creating industry-grade blockchains. Blockchain is being used in many businesses not just as a cryptocurrency but also as a tool to protect data, privacy, and authentication methods. Because it increases the level of confidence in technical use, it becomes easier to transact with unidentified parties, thus extending markets and driving up demand for goods and services, which can increase profitability. It causes a lot of hurdles for simple and adaptable adoption in modern organizations, as well as many opportunities to preserve and develop opportunities. In this post, the specifics are laid down while taking into account both aspects of blockchain usage.

Keywords: blockchain, defi, peer-to-peer transaction, DLT, scalability, security, interoperability

Introduction

In essence, blockchain is a database system with characteristics that, when considered individually, are not special to it, but which when taken together constitute a technological advance in the way digital information is stored, validated, and traded. The fact that blockchain is a sort of distributed ledger technology (DLT) accounts for the majority of its fundamental characteristics (Banafa, 2017). In contrast to traditional centralized methods, DLTs like blockchains distribute copies of the ledger database among the network's nodes, requiring each to log new transactions and take part in a consensus procedure to concur on ledger revisions. Another differentiation for

blockchain is its distinctive data format. In contrast to traditional databases, which store data in rows, columns, and files, a blockchain stores it in blocks that are connected and encrypted.

Due to the immutability provided by the data block and transaction-verification processes, it is almost mathematically impossible to alter the data or interrupt transactions. Because there is no central authority that bad events might use to break it, it is immune to data redundancy and transparency thanks to its distributed copies. Due to its unique nature, the ethical use of blockchain technology is highly accepted now in many business domains (see Fig 1) (Consensys, 2019; Dash, 2014). According to Gartner, the market for cryptocurrencies will be worth \$2 trillion by 2022. By 2027, 10% of the global gross domestic product, according to McKinsey, may come from blockchain transactions (Consensys, 2019). But it's time to have a systematic review of the pros and cons of this technology and how it will be beneficial for modern enterprises.

Fig 1. Blockchain spectrum and its usability. Adopted from (Consensys, 2019)

Types of Blockchain Technology

There are four types of blockchain technology available in the market. The many blockchain varieties are defined by how open or closed they are to letting participants accomplish the blockchain's primary tasks (Ertz & Boily, 2019), which include conducting transactions on it and confirming the veracity of each block that is added to it.

- **Public Blockchain:** A public blockchain is open to all users and does not require authorization to participate. This particular blockchain is the one where cryptocurrencies are stored. It's also the slowest since there are so many players in the blockchain's consensus process, which makes data verification time-consuming.

- **Private Blockchain:** This sort of blockchain typically has the same decentralization and peer-to-peer architecture as public blockchain but on a much smaller scale, which improves performance. It operates on a closed network, frequently under the control of a single institution. Ironically, because the owner or central node determines what is genuine, trust is lower than on a public blockchain. Because it's simpler for a few nodes to control the consensus mechanism that validates transactions, security can also be weakened. To date, the majority of well-known blockchain implementations are on private blockchains (Mohanta, 2019).
- **Hybrid Blockchain:** A hybrid blockchain, as may be expected, incorporates features of both public and private blockchains. With links to the public side still maintained, organizations can utilize it to segment some data and transactions behind a permission scheme. Its speed is better than public blockchains, but risk and integrity issues are better than public ones (Jimoh et al., 2019).
- **Consortium Blockchain:** This blockchain technology is similar to a private blockchain but managed by a group as opposed to a single entity. Compared to a private blockchain, there is less security vulnerability, but only one node is in charge of transaction validation.

Is Blockchain Beneficial for Business?

Modern business demands high data or transaction security, trust, and transparency (Dash et al., 2016). To solve these points, blockchain is the only technology that stands out. Blockchain removes third-party or middlemen to automate processes that often save time, cost, and effort. Blockchain also acts as a catalyst to save IT and labor costs, secure financial transactions, and enable new lines of business. Its benefits derive primarily from the trust that blockchain generates as well as from the privacy, security, data integrity, and transparency that it has by design. Dealing with unidentified parties is made possible by the degree of confidence in a blockchain, thus extending markets and the demand for goods and services, providing data security which in turn might increase profitability in the long run (Farion et al., 2019). Blockchain benefits to enterprises are outlined below.

- **Tokenization:** By turning assets into tokens, a wider range of assets, including industrial machinery, carbon credits, and digital art, become tradable online.
- **Innovation:** The unique characteristics of blockchain can be used to solve long-standing issues like evaluating academic credentials.

- **Decentralization:** Decentralized management is advantageous in situations when organizations must collaborate with one another, yet no one wants to be accountable for system upkeep, such as supply chains and research communities.
- **Trust and Security:** Blockchain enables trust between parties and its architecture can provide the best data security for organizations to protect client and enterprise NPI data which is nearly impossible to hack (Grover et al., 2019).
- **Scalability and Traceability:** In the supply chain or financial industry, both scalability and traceability matter when a business needs to track and trace the effectiveness of any service. So, using blockchain, those demands can be fulfilled with ease (Farion et al., 2019).
- **Reduced cost:** The blockchain process is very efficient and automated it helps in reducing cost by easing the process of tracking, reporting, and auditing. It eliminates intermediaries so transactions are handled faster without any bottlenecks (Grover et al., 2019).

Challenges in Implementing Blockchain

Due to several technical, organizational, skill, and regulatory constraints, implementing blockchain initiatives in an enterprise can be a challenging task (Chen et al., 2017). The following are some of the main difficulties that businesses may experience when putting blockchain ideas into practice:

- i. **Lack of technical expertise:** Due to its complexity, blockchain technology may not be fully understood by all decision-makers within enterprises. Gaining acceptance and support for blockchain efforts may be challenging as a result.
- ii. **Regulatory redtaping:** Blockchain legislation is still developing, and compliance can be difficult, particularly in sectors with strong laws like finance and healthcare (Grover et al., 2019).
- iii. **Compatibility issues for integration:** It's possible that different blockchain platforms and protocols won't work together. Businesses must pick the appropriate blockchain technology and guarantee that it can be integrated properly with their current systems.
- iv. **Low scalability:** There are some known bottlenecks in some blockchain networks and scalability problems with some blockchain networks, particularly in terms of transaction throughput. The blockchain may become slower and costlier to use as more transactions are added to it. Most businesses still use legacy systems. It can be challenging to integrate

these systems with blockchain technology and may call for considerable changes (Gurtu & Johny, 2019).

- v. **Security concerns still exist:** Despite being regarded as secure, assaults are still possible on the public blockchain. Organizations need to handle potential security issues such as private key management and smart contract flaws.
- vi. **Costs of implementing and managing:** A blockchain network's setup and upkeep can be costly. For certain firms, the expenses of hardware, software, development, and ongoing maintenance might be a major deterrent. Creating a private blockchain needs money, consistency, and technical expertise to be called a success (Chen et al., 2017).
- vii. **Talent shortage:** In the IT sector, there is a lack of qualified blockchain developers, architects, and specialists with multi-domain knowledge. It can be difficult to attract and keep people with the requisite understanding.
- viii. **Adoption and customer expectations:** It can be challenging to persuade users, both internal and external, to use blockchain-based solutions. Important considerations include user experience and how simple it is to sign up for the blockchain platform.
- ix. **Consensus mechanism:** It can be difficult to select the best consensus mechanism, which has consequences for security, scalability, and energy usage (such as Proof of Work or Proof of Stake).
- x. **Data governance:** To avoid data manipulation and guarantee data accuracy, a blockchain network must establish data governance regulations. This necessitates thorough preparation and execution.
- xi. **Network reliability and change management:** Blockchain networks ought to be highly reliable and available. Operations might be hampered, and trust can be damaged by downtime or network instability.
- xii. At the same time, an organization may need to undergo a considerable culture shift to implement blockchain technology. Employees and users must adjust to new procedures and methods of operation to get the most out of it.
- xiii. **Token Economics:** Organizations must carefully evaluate the economic model, token distribution, and incentives if a blockchain project uses tokens or cryptocurrencies to ensure the project's success.

- xiv. **Intellectual property issue:** Prospective on using blockchain and cryptocurrencies are changing globally and that varies from country to country. It has been observed that projects involving blockchain frequently face legal and intellectual property issues, particularly when several parties are working together on the project.

It is highly recommended that when implementing blockchain initiatives, businesses should do extensive research, create a concise strategy, and work with knowledgeable partners or consultants to overcome these issues. To keep compliance and success, it's also critical to stay current on legislative changes and best practices within the sector.

Best Practices Implementing Blockchain in Enterprises

It takes a keen understanding of the benefits of blockchain and a narrow focus on the issues it is best equipped to solve in order to generate a favorable return on investment from what are likely to be expensive blockchain projects (Polkowski et al., 2018).

- Clearly understand the use case and what needs to be solved using Blockchain technology.
- Smartly choose the right fit technology or platform for your organizational needs.
- Focus less on the latest technology and more on the network with the largest user base.
- Don't spend time, resources, or labor on a blockchain solution to solve a problem that has already been found using another technique. Resources are wasted, and risk is increased.
- Do your proper due diligence and proof of concept before huge investment in blockchain projects.

Future of Blockchain for Business Use

Along with AI, Cloud, and IoT, blockchain is one of a select few cloud-based technologies that are seen as crucial to digital transformation and the "intelligent" organization. Blockchain is becoming extremely popular, particularly as the complete Web 3.0 idea is realized. Parts of Web 3.0 are starting to be implemented by major manufacturers, and the excitement around it could be enough to increase demand for blockchain. Blockchain-based goods and services are being promoted more and more as Web 3.0 tools. Financial sectors are the most efficient users of this technology, and it is used mostly in all business operations (Hu et al., 2018).

The combination of blockchain with AI is one of the most exciting blockchain trends. Huge volumes of data are required for AI to use machine learning algorithms to identify patterns, forecast

future events, and "learn" how to replace tasks currently performed by people. Blockchain technology has the potential to release a deluge of fresh data, in part by giving users the privacy and protection they require to feel comfortable disclosing more of their personal information. AI, in turn, might increase the effectiveness of the laborious consensus and verification process used in blockchain technology (Morkunas et al., 2019). The future and potential of blockchain technology look promising to solve day-to-day business problems.

Conclusion

The global business model is quickly evolving for growth and sustainability as data volume, rule complexity, legal procedures, and customer demands rise. It encourages businesses to step outside of their comfort zones and develop novel, scalable, and effective products and services. The best technologies for the digitization process in this area are blockchain, IoT, and artificial intelligence. Blockchain is here to stay and will continue to help companies grow. However, picking the best technology and business fit is crucial, and that must be done carefully.

Blockchain use is rising in healthcare, supply chain, and Fintech domains. Despite all of this, this technology has become widely accepted and is now a regular topic of conversation in the business media. Blockchain's suitability for commercial application has been questioned by digital currency fraud, bankruptcies, and hacks, but the technology is still developing. Vendors of IT services continue to make investments in it and persuade clients that it merits a significant place in their business and IT plans.

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